

Knowledge integration actions: artisans from the Wayúu Majalí Community in La Guajira

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Summary

Knowledge integration actions propose a paradigm shift in the incorporation of technology in vulnerable communities. Instead of receiving external solutions, these communities become protagonists of their own technological development, taking advantage of their local knowledge and promoting their autonomy. Under this premise, the Universidad de La Guajira (Colombia) and the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (Spain) carried out an innovation and entrepreneurship workshop with 32 female artisans from the Wayúu community Majali in Riohacha, La Guajira.

The three-day workshop focused on strengthening the artisans' abilities to optimize their production processes and explore new development possibilities for their businesses. Through a participatory methodology based on work groups and visual tools, topics such as identifying business opportunities, analysing business models using the Canvas scheme, process optimization, inventory and cost management, and exploring new marketing strategies were explored.

As a result, the artisans not only acquired new tools and knowledge, but also identified concrete opportunities for improvement in their businesses, thus strengthening their empowerment and the sustainability of their activities. The workshop demonstrated the potential of knowledge integration actions to promote technological and social development from the heart of the communities, recognizing and valuing their knowledge and experience.

1. Introduction

Knowledge integration actions

The action described in this document is part of a broader initiative, the development of what we call knowledge integration actions. This approach arises from the observation that, in many cases, the incorporation of technology into vulnerable population environments does not achieve sustainable results. The reasons for this phenomenon are diverse and it is difficult to say that one strategy or another will guarantee better results. However, it is reasonable to think that a community-led approach is more likely to generate lasting results.

Indeed, it is our conviction that that technological innovation reaches its full potential when it emerges from within communities. Knowledge integration actions propose a paradigm shift where, instead of receiving external solutions, communities become protagonists of their own technological development.

This approach is based on the idea that knowledge is built together. Instead of external experts imposing their ideas, the communities are encouraged to take the reins of innovation. In this model, external technicians act as facilitators, providing their technical knowledge, but not directing the process. It is the community, with their knowledge and experience, that identify the problems that need solving and decides how to address them. This is a paradigm shift where the leading role falls on the community, recognizing its capacity to generate solutions adapted to their own needs and realities.

This model of innovation from within implies:

- Recognizing the value of local knowledge. Communities have a deep understanding of their environment, needs and resources. This knowledge is essential for the development of relevant and sustainable technologies.
- Facilitating knowledge transfer. Provide communities with access to information, technical training and the tools necessary to develop their own technological solutions.
- Promoting autonomy. Foster the capacity of communities to manage their own technologies, maintain them and adapt them over time.
- Promoting social innovation. Stimulate the creation of technologies that respond to the social and environmental challenges of communities, promoting inclusion, equity and sustainability.

For the development of this type of action, an active, group-based working method is key, as it promotes participation, the exchange of knowledge, joint decision-making and the strengthening of the social fabric. In this way, the creation of relevant, sustainable technologies that respond to the communities' challenges is encouraged.

Knowledge integration actions represent an opportunity to build a more just, equitable and sustainable technological future, where technology is put at the service of the well-being of all people and the planet.

Context of the action

Building upon the concept of knowledge integration, the Universidad de La Guajira, Colombia, and the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Spain, are developing joint actions aimed at indigenous communities, as well as other vulnerable groups, in the department of La Guajira.

La Guajira, a Colombian region rich in natural resources, experiences complex social, political and economic dynamics. La Guajira is home to the Wayuu indigenous people, who make up 45% of the region's population. They mainly live in rural areas and represent a cultural bastion for the country. The cultural wealth of the region contrasts with low socioeconomic indicators that force the population to live in the midst of many inequalities and to experience gaps that limit their development. In the area where the actions were carried out, more than half (58.1%) of households do not have basic needs in housing, education, health and public services. This indicator of unmet basic needs indicates that the rural area (81.9%) presents a much more critical situation than the urban area (47.1%), worsening the living conditions of the population¹.

Among the topics covered in the integration actions is energy planning. In this area, work is done collaboratively with communities to explore the use of renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind energy, that are compatible with their environment and culture.

Another priority line of activity is innovation and entrepreneurship, particularly female entrepreneurship. The objective, in this case, is to empower entrepreneurs, both established and aspiring, to optimize processes, manage resources efficiently and develop sustainable ventures, based on their culture, traditions and knowledge, through exchange and joint work.

¹ Data from DANE (National Administrative Department of Statistics, Colombia) from 2018.

The action described in this document was developed at the Riohacha Campus of the Universidad de La Guajira, on September 24, 25 and 26, 2024, under the name "Innovation and Entrepreneurship Workshop. Process Optimization and Efficient Resource Management". The action was developed for women artisans from a Wayúu community, the Majalí community.

On behalf of the universities, the following participated in the action: professors Clara Sarith Amaya Marmol, Judith Feria and Ruth Amaya Marmol, from the Universidad de La Guajira, and professors Paula Andrea Gómez Botero and Jordi Olivella Nadal, from the team of the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya^{2,3}.

Figure 1. Photograph of the whole group

2. Content, methodology and participants

Content and methodology

The action was designed as an innovation and entrepreneurship action aimed primarily, although not exclusively, at women in the Wayúu communities. In the case described here, it was developed exclusively with women artisans from the Wayúu community Majalí. A detailed schedule of each day was defined, with the understanding that activities would be adjusted to suit the group's dynamics. The schedule is shown in Table 1.

² We must thank Beatriz Elena Amaya Mendoza, coordinator of the Entrepreneurship Coordination at the Universidad de La Guajira, for the opportunity and support; as well as the members of the DESTACAR group from the same university, Marlon Bastidas Barranco, Andrés D. Vides Prado, Albert Deluque Pinto and Aduar Camargo Medina; as well as Bruno Domenech Lera and Laia Ferrer Martí, who complete the UPC team in these actions.

³ The activities of the members of the team of the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya were funded by the Centre de Cooperació al Desenvolupament of the university itself, as part of the project "Actions for the integration of knowledge with leaders of indigenous communities of La Guajira for the implementation of technology (project 2024-A007)".

Table 1. Activities and schedules of the action

	ACTIVITY	SCHEDULES
Day 1	Welcome and Introductions	09:00 - 10:00
	Workshop 1: Identifying Business Opportunities	10:00 - 12:00
	Lunch Break	12:00 - 13:00
	Workshop 2: Basic Strategic Planning	13:00 - 15:00
	Break (Traditional snacks and drinks)	15:00 - 15:30
	Workshop 3: Supply and Supplier Management	15:30 - 17:00
Day 2	Workshop 4: Work Organization and Productivity	09:00 - 10:00
	Workshop 5: Inventory Management	10:00 - 12:00
	Lunch Break	12:00 - 13:00
	Workshop 6: Basic Financial Control	13:00 - 15:00
	Break (Traditional snacks and drinks)	15:00 - 15:30
	Workshop 7: Data Collection and Analysis	15:30 - 17:00
Day 3	Workshop 8: Making Informed Decisions	09:00 - 10:00
	Workshop 9: Action Planning: Tools	10:00 - 12:00
	Lunch Break	12:00 - 13:00
	Workshop 10: Action Planning: results	13:00 - 15:00
	Break (Traditional snacks and drinks)	15:00 - 15:30
	Workshop 11: Accessing Resources and Financing & Promoting Local Products & Closing Ceremony	15:30 - 17:00

Methodology

To ensure the full participation of all participants, the action's methodology centred around small working groups. These groups were intentionally designed to include individuals with strong Spanish language skills to facilitate communication with university members. While activities conducted by the entire group were always in Spanish (a language understood by all participants), discussions within the smaller working groups took place in the Wayúu language. This approach ensured that all team members could participate without language barriers.

The structure of the different activities (or workshops, in the terminology adopted to adapt to that used by the Universidad de La Guajira in its seminars) was consistent and included the following:

- Presentation of the topic to be discussed, basically by members of the Universidad de La Guajira, closer to the context of the community.
- Discussion of the working groups. To facilitate and standardize the presentation of the work and the results of the discussion, templates were provided for each activity.
- Discussion by the whole group, with presentation of the results of the working groups and obtaining general results. Visual aids such as a blackboard and self-adhesive labels on a wall were used to reflect these general results.

Figure 2 shows the working groups developing one of the activities.

Figure 2. Working groups carrying out one of the activities

Characteristics and interests of participants

Thirty-two artisans from the community participated in the action, forming work groups of 5 or 6 members. To foster group identity, they were asked to choose a name for each of them. Table 2 presents some data on the different groups. Specifically, it indicates the level of education and the number of participants in each group who had a cell phone. The table shows a roughly equal distribution of participants across three education levels: no education, primary education, and secondary education. Just over half of the participants had access to a cell phone.

All groups included several educated members with cell phones, ensuring a degree of homogeneity in this regard. This homogeneity was likely influenced by the requirement that each group include members with strong Spanish language skills. It is reasonable to assume that those with higher education levels and greater economic means were more likely to be fluent in Spanish.

Table 2. Groups, studies and cell phone availability

Cluster	Members	Without studies	Primary	Secondary	They have a cell phone
Orb-weaving spiders	5	1	2	2	3
Craftsmanship of the soul	6	4	1	1	3
Ancestral essence	5	3		2	3
Backpack Weavers	5		3	2	2
Weaving dreams	6	2	3	1	4
Weaving traditions	5	1	3	1	3
Total	32	11	12	9	18

Before commencing the planned activities, each work group identified the products they crafted and their main interests regarding the action. They displayed the various products on a mural using adhesive labels (see Figure 3). While the artisans produced a wide range of items, backpacks constituted a significant portion of their output.

Figure 3. Products made by the community's artisans⁴

Table 3 shows the interests each group expressed regarding the upcoming action. Their primary interests focused on enhancing product appeal and expanding sales beyond their current market—the merchants of Riohacha's Nuevo Mercado⁵.

Table 3. Interests of participants

Cluster	Interests
Orb-weaving spiders	Learn more designs of each product. Learning to further improve products. Learn how to have a good sale. Learn how to maintain the product. Learn to negotiate the price of the product.
Craftsmanship of the soul	Sharing knowledge to improve designs. That crafts have a better price. Have more clientele.
Ancestral essence	Implement fair trade practices that benefit artisan communities. Combining traditional techniques with modern designs. exchange of knowledge to improve the designs of the artisans.
Backpack weavers	Have a new place to go to sell the products, since now you earn very little. Knitting backpacks well and having good designs.
Weaving dreams	Learn more to be able to do a better job and have a better quality product. Have a channel to be able to take the products out of the city. Promotion of products online.
Weaving traditions	Sell the backpacks elsewhere for a higher price. Sell more quantities. Learn more designs to make your backpacks more eye-catching.

3. Development of action and results

The event took place over three days, basically following the schedule shown in Table 1. As planned, Day 1 dealt with commercial and product aspects, Day 2 focused on operational and cost issues, and Day 3 was devoted to the development of improvement proposals and an information session on financing and vocational training possibilities.

⁴ Products shown in the figure: hammock, gauze, backpack, key chains, sash, plate, bathing suits, laces, headscarves, fringes, blanket embroidery, bracelets, tassels, wallets, bows, purses, shorts, blouses, tablecloths and veils.

⁵ The Nuevo Mercado (new market) of Riohacha is the most important market square in the capital of La Guajira, Colombia. It is a vibrant and lively place where you can find a wide variety of products, from fresh food to traditional crafts.

Day 1

The first activity challenged groups to identify business opportunities within their field and analyse their skills to leverage those opportunities. The introductory presentation included the theoretical possibilities of producing non-traditional fashion products or fulfilling designer commissions. These examples served merely as potential alternatives, not recommendations. While these ideas did not spark extensive debate, some participants affirmed the existing value of local crafts.

Table 4 presents the opportunities and ideas identified by each group, largely aligning with their previously expressed interests. However, these possibilities were more concrete, with a continued emphasis on commercial themes and expanding sales to new cities.

Table 4. Opportunities and ideas

Cluster	Opportunities and ideas
Orb-weaving spiders	Gain more knowledge about sales and how to promote products. Meet people who buy the products Look for outlets, where to sell more. Get help with networks to sell more. Improve the product. Conduct demonstrations. Give a new use to the product.
Craftsmanship of the soul	Leave La Guajira to sell products at better prices, like Cartagena or Santa Sarta.
Ancestral essence	Contact with merchants who can help improve sales, both nationally and internationally. Participate in fairs. Expand the product range in both styles and sizes. Sell abroad.
Backpack weavers	Buy materials to make backpacks that you can sell in places like Valledupar. Having the opportunity to travel, for example, to Cabo de la Vela, to improve the product.
Weaving dreams	Have someone who can guide you on how to go and sell at festivals outside the city.
Weaving traditions	Advertise and sell through social media. Travel to places like Palomino, Valledupar or Santa Marta to sell.

The groups shared their discussion results on key topics, skills, and opportunities with the entire group, recording the main ideas on a mural with self-adhesive labels (see Figure 4). This highlighted the central ideas regarding interests and opportunities previously detailed. The artisans also identified key skills, including speed, sociability, empathy, physical endurance, planning, concentration, and creativity. This is a set of personal qualities that, in the light of the established dialogue, they really possessed.

Figure 4. Topics of interest, skills and opportunities detected⁶

Next, the working groups prepared business model analyses based on a Canvas scheme, focusing on commercial aspects. Figure 5 illustrates an analysis by one of the groups.

Figure 5. Canvas developed by the group Spider Weavers

COORDINACIÓN DE EMPRENDIMIENTO, INNOVACIÓN Y DESARROLLO EMPRESARIAL				
MODELO DE NEGOCIO TEAM CANVAS				
Nombre(s) Del(os) Emprendedor(es)		arañas tejedoras		
Modelo De Negocio:		mochilas		
Problema	Solución	Propuesta De Valor Única	Ventaja Especial	Segmentos De Clientes
Necesidades que tiene el cliente para comprar: - diseños únicos - ocupan más espacio - es lavable	Son duraderos - muy coloridos - exclusivos - todos los tamaños	Cliente extranjero Son hechos a mano con historia. Cliente local Son diseños únicos Clientes masivos	diseños con historia. diseños únicos - diseño con calidad	- distribuidores - clientes que compra al mayor - clientes para vender
Alternativas Existentes: - Waterpas - Sandalia - Vela: pantoletas - mochilas: maletín - moñas: gancho - Manilla: pulsera	Métricas Claves: medidas de las mochilas: mediana Plato: 15. altura: 35 tiempo: un día	Cliente distribuidor Son garantizados de buena calidad.	Canales: Viajan a vender - venta a las turísticas. - venta por internet - ferias y pabellones - viajes, publicidad,	

⁶ The following are indicated in the figure: topics of interest (place of sale, economic support, quality, inventories, Internet, negotiation, capital, prices, sales, purchases, sales channels, designs, persuasion and sales), skills (speed, sociability and empathy, physical resistance, planning, concentration and creativity) and opportunities (traveling with the products, attitude, travel logistics and location, commercial techniques, fairs and events, and sales knowledge)

The entire group analysed the core commercial aspects of their businesses based on the working groups' business model analyses. Specifically, customer needs, customer segments, value propositions and sales channels were assessed. The results were again included in a mural, an image of which is shown in Figure 6. This analysis expanded upon the previously expressed concerns and informed the proposals and actions analysed in a later phase.

Figure 6. Business aspects identified in the Canvas⁷

To conclude Day 1, the groups discussed supplies, listing the materials they used and their suppliers. The number of available suppliers proved limited, primarily concentrated in Riohacha's Nuevo Mercado. A purchasing negotiation simulation generated significant interest.

Day 2

As planned, Day 2 focused on operational and cost issues. Using a provided template, the working groups analyzed the operations involved in one of their main activities—the production and sale of a chosen product. The template guided them to detail each step, noting the description, who performs it, average time, tools and materials used, relevant data, and any problems identified.

Figure 7 shows an example of one group's operational analysis. These analyses encouraged reflection on their work processes, including aspects they typically overlooked, according to the artisans themselves.

⁷ They are indicated in the figure: Customer needs (comfort/resistance, bringing a gift to the country/city of origin, dressing other people, looking good and fashion, capacity and quality, exclusivity and history, and memory of the trip), Customer segments (foreign tourists, local tourists, local customers, shops in the coastal area, distributors, designers, exporters and marketers in the area), Value propositions (selling with history, customization on request, selling punctually and confidently to distributors, showing the virtue of handmade, quality and variety, innovative materials and colors, explaining the design, innovative design and design with images specific to the context) and sales channels (travel and exhibition in other places and cities, websites and the Internet, Facebook, Tik Tok, fairs, Instagram, Mercado Libre, shipping by carriers).

Figure 7. Analysis of operations of one of the groups

ARANAS TEJEDORAS						
CHINCHORRO ANÁLISIS DE OPERACIONES CHINCHORRO						
Enumeración de los pasos	Descripción del paso: ¿Qué sucede?	¿Quién lo realiza?	Tiempo promedio	Herramientas / Materiales utilizados	Datos relevantes: Cantidad producida	Problemas identificados
1	Elegir tipo de chinchorro. Colores, diseños	Tejedor	10 minutos	La mente. La vista. Aplicaciones por internet	1 chinchorro	Leve mal ajuste de cables
2	Comprar hilo tijeras varillas metro.	"	2 horas	el dinero de préstamo	1	Manos cortadas. Falta de materiales buenos
3	Preparar metales	"	3 horas	manos hilos	"	Consumo de hilo en las manos
4	Colocar los varones	"	15 minutos	varas de maderas	"	"
n	organizar	"	tres días	para de medir hilos	"	"
1	hacer en el medio	"	5 días	hilos	"	"
2	hacer cabecera	"	2 días	hilos	"	"
3	comenzar cabecera	"	1 hora	hilos	"	"
4	Probar chinchorro	"	10 minutos	Cabilla y personas	"	Puede de fractos del chinchorro
n	vender	"	un mes	Clientes	"	Falta de clientes

Continuing with aspects of the operational area, the next activity consisted of analysing the status of their inventories and their evolution over the course of a month. It should be noted that the day before, the groups had been asked to collect inventory information from at least one of their members. Again, they worked based on a template. The result of the work of one of the groups is shown in Figure 8. The members of the community acknowledged that the inventory management they currently carried out was often not very detailed and could be improved.

Figure 8. Inventory prepared by one of the groups

Tejedoras de Sueños 1-30/09											
PLANTILLA DE INVENTARIO											
Item	Nombre del Producto	Categoría	Cantidad Inicial	Entradas	Salidas	Stock Actual	Costo Unitario	Valor Total	Fecha Último Movimiento	Proveedor	Ubicación en Almacén
	Modala 40.	bolsas	40.	1	7	33	\$35000	245.000	15/09		Artesanía Wayuú
	Moñitos 10.	Abrazos	10	1	2	8	\$10000	20.000	10/09		
	gatos 10.	abrazos	10	1	4	6	\$12000	42.000	17/09		
	Cordón 15	Abrazos	15	1	7	8	\$5000	35.000	17/09		
	llaveros 25.	Abrazos	25	1	5	20	\$2000	10.000	17/09		

The last activity of the day centred on a particularly important topic: cost analysis. The working groups explored an unconventional approach, calculating net income per hour worked. This calculation considered sales revenue, material costs, and an estimated cost of sales.

This particular method was chosen because both income and the various costs were largely beyond the artisans' control. Moreover, the artisans did not typically view time spent on production as a true cost. Therefore, a traditional cost analysis, calculating a cost per hour and determining profitability, would not have provided useful information in this context. Instead, focusing on income per hour worked could significantly influence their decisions regarding which products to prioritize.

Table 5 presents the results for different types of backpacks. These results demonstrate that income per hour worked can vary considerably based on the size of the backpack. The analysis was also extended to other product types, revealing even greater variations. Generally, the less common and more intricate products generated a much higher income per hour worked compared to the more frequently produced items. While the artisans were aware of some differences in profitability between products, they were surprised by the magnitude of these differences. The calculations also highlighted some disparities in yield that were entirely new to them. To protect the artisans' commercial strategy, not all specific data is included in this report.

Table 5. Calculation of net income per hour for certain products

Product	Large backpack	Medium backpack 1	Medium backpack 2	Small backpack
Gross income ⁸	\$150,000	\$35,000	\$20,000	\$10,000
Material units	20	10	5	3
Material unit cost	\$2,000	\$2,000	\$2,000	\$2,000
Total material cost	\$40,000	\$20,000	\$10,000	\$6,000
Cost of sales ⁹	\$30,000	\$7,000	\$4,000	\$2,000
Gross income	\$80,000	\$8,000	\$6,000	\$2,000
Working hours	35	12	5	3
Net income per hour	\$2,286	\$667	\$1,200	\$667

Day 3

The third day focused on preparing proposals for improvement, which involved considering all the analyses carried out and transforming them into concrete plans. The working groups chose, from among the different types of possible projects, which one they were going to develop, so as to cover the different aspects that had been worked on in the previous days.

Once the working groups had prepared the different proposals, they were presented to the entire group. Figure 9 shows the presentations, in which the main aspects of each proposal were shared.

⁸ Gross income refers to the income obtained from the sale of a unit.

⁹ The cost of sales was established, based on the available data, at 20% of gross income.

Figure 9. Presentation of the projects of each group

The proposals addressed a range of areas: product improvements (Weaving spiders), inventory management (Craftsmanship of the soul), costs (Ancestral essence), distribution (Backpack weavers), standardization (Weaving dreams) and sales through social networks (Weaving traditions). The proposals include commercial aspects, which were already a concern for the community participants before the action, and also operational and financial aspects, which were proposed in the previous sessions. Table 6 includes phrases taken from the different presentations.

Table 6. Phrases taken from the presentations of the projects of each group

Cluster	Projects
Orb-weaving spiders	<i>The first thing is to gather all the members of my community and there we see who has internet, who can request courses to improve the fabrics, and the techniques to use the applications to connect with designers and thus learn new designs. We think about making different products, not just new designs, but thinking about other products. Some crafts can be combined to make different designs. For example, adding more decorations, buying other materials, such as with gold threads. Also earrings, necklaces and other types of products.</i>
Craftsmanship of the soul	<i>Inventory management system. In other words, generating a template so that everyone can keep track of their inventories.</i>
Ancestral essence	<i>Cost reduction. The goal is to improve the production process through training for technical teams. Buy materials in bulk, visit the supplier, call them so that when we go to buy, they already have the product on hold. The plan is to carefully analyze the sale price, reduce costs, and organize the products well.</i>
Backpack Weavers	<i>The objective of the product is to manage the place where it will be sold and the transport. It is about grouping the products of the community. And also traveling to new cities where the products are sold.</i>
Weaving dreams	<i>Standardization of measurements for each product. The aim would be to meet with the community to establish a measurement for each size of backpack and for each drawing. The objective of the project is to save threads of material, save time and also improve the process. The conditions of the process can also be standardized so that everyone can take the same amount of time making each of the products.</i>
Weaving traditions	<i>The project consists of using social media to advertise our product. We have to teach people how to use the networks, create profiles and, every time we make a product, upload a photo or a video. We have to check social media constantly to see if they write to us.</i>

Finally, an information session was held on financing and professional training possibilities by a representative of SENA¹⁰.

4. Conclusions

We believe the workshop successfully empowered the artisans, positioning them as the protagonists of their own development. They actively participated in analyzing their businesses, identifying opportunities, and generating solutions. The artisans' local knowledge—their experience in product creation, their understanding of the local market, and their unique skills—was recognized and leveraged as the foundation for analysis and improvement proposals.

This fostered a reciprocal exchange of knowledge. The universities provided tools and methodologies for business analysis, while the artisans contributed their practical expertise and insights into the local context. This exchange enriched the process and led to more relevant and effective solutions.

Furthermore, we believe the workshop generated tangible benefits for the artisans. They identified new business opportunities, optimized their processes, gained a deeper understanding of costs, and explored new marketing strategies. These outcomes can contribute to increased income and the long-term sustainability of their ventures.

The participatory methodology, based on working groups and visual tools, was crucial to the workshop's success. It facilitated active participation, the exchange of ideas, and the generation of innovative proposals.

We are convinced that this initiative will have both a short-term and long-term impact on the artisans' activities, a sentiment echoed by the participants themselves. Looking ahead, we plan to follow up on the artisans' proposals, providing continued support and evaluating their impact. We also aim to replicate this workshop model with other communities.

¹⁰ SENA (National Learning Service) is a Colombian public institution that offers free training to Colombian citizens in a wide variety of technical, technological and complementary areas.